

Classification and Interpretation of Two-Dimensional Electronic Spectra Using Convolutional Neural Networks

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1 Abstract

This study applies a convolutional neural network (CNN) to the interpretation of two-dimensional electronic spectra (2DES), and establishes a program framework covering spectral-data preprocessing, model training, and testing. Using simulated 2DES as model input, this work interprets excitation-state energy difference (Δ), coupling constant (J), and dipole angle.

2 Research Motivation and Research Question

As deep-learning algorithms have become increasingly mature, and hardware performance has advanced substantially, deep learning—which requires high-speed parallel computation—has gained practical room for application. In recent years, machine learning, artificial intelligence, and deep learning have become major trends, and many successful cases have appeared across industries and research fields, rapidly replacing complex analytical tasks that previously required human effort.

In chemistry, spectroscopy is an indispensable tool for studying the physical and chemical properties of molecules, such as IR and visible spectroscopy. However, spectral interpretation is often difficult because sample purity, instrument noise, experimental operation, and the sample’s own structure and properties can prevent spectra from being clearly distinguishable. This is especially true for recently developed two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy methods: due to system complexity and spectral-resolution limits, the resulting spectra often lack clear peak features, making interpretation very challenging (Fig. 1). By leveraging the ability of neural networks (hereafter, “the network”) to process and learn from large amounts of data, I aim to use a convolutional neural network to read spectra and directly output sample properties of interest to researchers, provide more quantitative spectral interpretation results, and extract additional factors that may influence spectral patterns.

Figure 1: Example 2DES with weakly distinguishable spectral features.

3 Literature Review and Discussion

Machine-learning applications in chemistry already have clear precedents, and many studies show that neural networks are broadly useful for research problems with complete datasets. In 2013,

Gregoire Montavon et al. (Ref. 2) trained models using commonly used *ab initio* parameters as inputs and predicted multiple ground-state and excited-state properties. Their performance was comparable to, and in some cases better than, previous methods, with shorter computation time. In 2017, Bing Huang and O. Anatole von Lilienfeld et al. (Ref. 3) used molecular structures to predict ground-state molecular energies and compared results with *ab initio* methods such as post-Hartree-Fock and density functional theory; they showed that models trained on very few small-molecule types could still predict larger-molecule energies effectively.

In addition, neural networks have particular strengths in image analysis. In 2018, Piotr Klukowski et al. (Ref. 4) used CNNs to predict 14 protein absorption peaks in NMR spectra, achieving accuracy above 80%. Salim Malek et al. (Ref. 5) had already applied CNN training to one-dimensional electronic excitation spectra in 2017, and their results showed strong capability in spectral feature extraction. Therefore, this project uses the image-processing strength of CNNs to train on two-dimensional spectra, aiming to resolve long-standing difficulties in spectral interpretation.

4 Principles

4.1 Two-Dimensional Electronic Spectroscopy (2DES) Data

All spectra used in this study were generated by the laboratory-developed 2DES simulation program. Its principle is four-wave mixing (Fig. 2): three laser pulses with different frequencies (k_1 , k_2 , k_3) excite the molecule at different times, distributing population among different excited states. The emission signal is then collected in the phase-matching direction

$$k_S = -k_1 + k_2 + k_3.$$

Fourier transforms are applied along coherence time (τ) and detection time (t), converting data from time domain to frequency domain and yielding excitation-absorption two-dimensional spectra.

Figure 2: Schematic principle of two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy.

4.2 Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

ANN is one way to implement machine-learning algorithms. By simulating and simplifying neural operation in the brain, it can process nonlinear multivariable regression and approximation problems. This method can be used for complex tasks that were previously performed by humans, such as classification, pattern recognition, and face recognition.

Figure 3: Basic three-layer ANN concept.

4.3 Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Model

CNN is a branch of ANN mainly used when the input format is image data. Because image data are extremely high-dimensional (each pixel can be treated as one dimension), computation becomes difficult. CNN effectively reduces required dimensionality and computational complexity. It consists of convolution, pooling, and fully connected layers; after the fully connected layer, the output proceeds in a standard ANN framework.

Figure 4: Convolution operation and feature extraction concept.

Its core process is as follows:

1. Convolution: perform one-to-one weighted summation between the input image and filters. Usually multiple filters are used, so multiple feature maps are generated.
2. Pooling: simplify feature maps to reduce errors caused by small translations or noise. For max pooling, the maximum value is retained in each $n \times n$ region while the others are discarded.
3. Fully connected layer: processed feature maps are flattened into an $n \times 1$ matrix and then fed into the ANN input layer for training.
4. After repeated convolution and pooling, one more fully connected layer is linked to the neural network; this forms the theoretical CNN architecture.

Figure 5: Key operations in CNN-based spectral learning.

5 Research Methods and Process

5.1 Dimer Model and Parameter Sampling

In this study, a dimer of bacteriochlorophyll *a* (Fig. 6) is considered and simulated as a coupled two-level dimer system composed of two transition dipoles (hereafter, dipoles). Here, μ_1 and μ_2 are the two transition dipole moments, and r is their relative-distance vector.

The total Hamiltonian is written as

$$H_T = H_S + H_B + H_{SB},$$

where H_S , H_B , and H_{SB} denote the system Hamiltonian, bath condition, and system-bath coupling, respectively. The major factors affecting 2DES are H_S and H_{SB} .

In H_S , 500 is the average excitation energy of the two dipoles, 2Δ is their excitation-energy difference, and J is the electronic coupling constant. The range of Δ is set to 0–500 cm^{-1} . The magnitude of J is related to the dipoles' relative position, direction, and magnitude, and is calculated as:

$$J(\mu_1, \mu_2, r) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left[\frac{\mu_1\mu_2}{r^3} - 3\frac{(\mu_1 \cdot r)(\mu_2 \cdot r)}{r^5} \right].$$

In this study, both dipole moments are set as $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 6.132$ debye, and r is sampled in the range 15–30 Å. Because only coupling within the 1-exciton manifold is considered, other off-diagonal terms are set to zero.

For H_{SB} , two identical Ohmic baths are coupled to the two dipoles, and the spectral function is:

$$J(\omega) = \gamma_0 \omega e^{-\omega/\omega_c}.$$

Here, γ_0 is coupling strength, ω is frequency, and ω_c is cut-off frequency. γ_0 is randomly sampled in the range 0.5–1.5.

To simulate system error, Gaussian-sampled static disorder is added to the excitation energies of the two dipoles, with standard deviation in the range 10–150 cm^{-1} .

With the above settings, a total of 1680 simulated 2DES were generated by the laboratory-developed 2DES simulator: 1176 for training and 504 for testing.

Figure 6: Coupled dimer system used in spectral simulation.

5.2 Machine-Learning Pipeline Construction

My main task was to build a pipeline-style program framework from spectrum-based training data, data preprocessing, model training, to testing results. The implementation was written in Python using NumPy, scikit-learn, TensorFlow, and Keras.

Pipeline steps:

1. Spectral training data: each spectrum generated by the 2DES simulator is paired with a parameter set. Spectra are used as training/testing inputs, and model parameters are used as labels (Δ , J , and dipole angle).
2. Data normalization: because the three labels have different orders of magnitude, each label value is divided by its maximum in the dataset to reduce training bias.
3. Split training/testing data: normalized data are split into training and testing sets using scikit-learn’s `train_test_split`.
4. Optimizer setup: Adam optimizer is used. The learning rate is set to 10^{-5} , with $\beta_1 = 0.2$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$.
5. Training model setup: the model uses three convolution + max-pooling layers, then flattening to a one-dimensional tensor, followed by a fully connected layer and output layer.

Figure 7: CNN model architecture used in this study for predicting Δ , J , and dipole angle from 2DES inputs.

6. Testing: the trained model takes the held-out testing spectra as input, predicts Δ , J , and dipole angle, and compares predictions with labels.
7. Renormalization: because labels were normalized during training, predicted values are scaled back to their original magnitudes.

6 Results and Discussion

In this study, the training model was used to train three labels (Δ , J , and dipole angle) simultaneously, and independent training was also performed for each label. Scatter plots were then generated for each prediction result. In addition, to examine whether the training model learned relationships among different labels, data points in each scatter plot were colored by the values of the other two labels.

6.1 Joint Training of Delta, J, and Dipole Angle

From Fig. 8, the prediction of Δ is consistent with expectation. The dominant factor affecting Δ is the more obvious diagonal-peak position in 2D spectra, which is relatively easy to distinguish, so interpretation is easier for the model. However, prediction results for J and dipole angle are not ideal. One likely reason is that the generated J values are relatively small; therefore, although a trend can be seen, the expected high accuracy is not achieved, and predictions are more concentrated in low- J regions.

This is also reflected in the J plot: spectra with larger Δ (green points) are predicted close to 0. Since larger Δ means larger energy separation between excited states, coupling is relatively less obvious, making interpretation more difficult for the model. Dipole angle is even harder to distinguish than Δ and J , and almost no clear trend is observed.

Figure 8: Prediction scatter plots under joint multi-target training.

6.2 Independent Training for Delta

Independent training for Δ (Fig. 9) shows clear overfitting: an unreasonable turning behavior appears at lower Δ , and deviation appears at higher Δ . After reducing the model's neural-layer depth to one layer, this phenomenon disappears, confirming the overfitting behavior.

Figure 9: Independent training results for Δ with different model depths.

6.3 Independent Training for J

Independent training for J (Fig. 10) is more accurate than in joint training (Fig. 8), indicating that simultaneous training still introduces partial bias and lowers accuracy, although this is not the only factor. The influence of different Δ values on interpretation accuracy is still present.

Figure 10: Independent training results for J .

6.4 Independent Training for Dipole Angle

Independent training for dipole angle (Fig. 11) still shows very low accuracy. This indicates that, in addition to bias from simultaneous training, other factors also prevent accurate interpretation of dipole angle from 2D spectra, or that more explicit information is required for reliable prediction.

Figure 11: Independent training results for dipole angle.

7 Conclusion

This work used a laboratory-developed 2DES simulator to generate 1680 spectra and established a complete pipeline for preprocessing, model training, and interpretation. The model achieved good performance for excitation-energy difference (Δ), while prediction of coupling constant (J) and dipole angle still has room for improvement.

Possible improvements include adding more informative descriptors and increasing dataset size to improve prediction accuracy.

8 References

1. Ramprasad, R.; Batra, R.; Pilania, G.; Mannodi-Kanakkithodi, A.; Kim, C. Machine learning in materials informatics: recent applications and prospects. *npj Comput. Mater.* 2017, 3(1).
2. Montavon, G.; Rupp, M.; Gobre, V.; et al. Machine learning of molecular electronic properties in chemical compound space. *New J. Phys.* 2013, 15(9).
3. Huang, B.; von Lilienfeld, O. A. The DNA of chemistry: scalable quantum machine learning with amons. *arXiv* 2017, 1707.04146v3.
4. Klukowski, P.; Augoff, M.; Zieba, M.; et al. NMRNet: a deep learning approach to automated peak picking of protein NMR spectra. *Bioinformatics* 2018, 34(15), 2590–2597.
5. Malek, S.; Melgani, F.; Bazi, Y. One-dimensional convolutional neural networks for spectroscopic signal regression. *J. Chemom.* 2018, 32(5).
6. Gao, H.; Lin, S.; Yang, Y.; Li, C.; Yang, M. Convolution neural network based on two-dimensional spectrum for hyperspectral image classification. *Sensors* 2018, 2018, 1–13.
7. Jonas, D. M. Two-dimensional femtosecond spectroscopy. *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* 2003, 54, 425–463.
8. Wang, X.; Wang, X. Unsupervised domain adaptation with coupled generative adversarial autoencoders. *Appl. Sci.* 2018, 8(12).

9. Schlau-Cohen, G. S.; Calhoun, T. R.; Ginsberg, N. S.; et al. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 2009, 113(46), 15352–15363.